

Consumers intention to use light weight cargo delivery by drones

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ABSTRACT

Drones are becoming increasingly popular. One of the reasons for this is the introduction of the 5G network. This development allows drones to fly autonomously due to the improved communication via 5G's lower latency and higher data-transfer speed network. This new phenomenon could make a change in the way packages get delivered.

In this article we discuss the potential of lightweight cargo drone delivery, by measuring which delivery and which product options influence the choice for drone delivery by customers. In order to measure these variables we conducted a survey among people living in the rural area.

The results from the survey shows that customers are more likely to pay more for same day deliveries when their packages get delivered via drones. Another remarkable result is that customers are likely to pay more if the delivery method is environmentally friendly and ensure a small carbon footprint. The results are generalizable for all new delivery methods. That is why we have set up a framework in which a variable of a new method can be placed.

Keywords

Drone delivery, 5G, Consumers, Technology acceptance, Framework

INTRODUCTION

In the last decade, there has been a change in the way consumers purchase their products. Instead of going to physical stores to purchase products, consumers order more products online that get delivered to the consumer's home. This convenient way of purchasing products has an EFFECT on the Dutch logistics sector, as the products not only get delivered to centralized locations (like stores or warehouse), but to decentralized locations as well (the individual consumer's home). This change

combined with the guarantee of retailers that ordered products get delivered to your home relatively fast (increased consumer's expectations) has increased the pressure on Dutch delivery services, which resulted in some occasions in several (heavy) delays (Emerce Logistics, 2018).

The Dutch delivery service PostNL stated that there has been an increase in the number of packages that are being ordered online. In 2018, PostNL delivered 251 million parcels, which is an increase of 10% compared to 2017 (PostNL, 2018). Around 64% of the Dutch population that's older than 12 years old ordered something online in 2012, which increased to 79,4% in 2018 (Centraal Bureau voor Statistiek, 2019). Additionally, PostNL expects that the number of parcels that need to be delivered will continue to increase (PostNL, 2018).

PROBLEM STATEMENT

New alternatives are currently being developed, which can reduce the pressure that is currently on the Dutch delivery services. According to McKinsey (2018), the introduction of a 5G network offers the possibility to set up a fully automated delivery process, that make the use of new delivery methods, such as droids, autonomous ground vehicles and drones, possible. According to Oliveira (2017), an automated delivery process is a process where the last-mile is delivered fully autonomous. This can be achieved with the help of drones or droids with no interaction of delivery drivers. This process can be further supported by automated delivery stations/boxes for when the client is not home, the package could be delivered there to further support the automation of the total process (Oliveira, 2017).

These new developments can have less of an impact on the infrastructure in the Netherlands, because autonomous delivery methods can have the potential to deliver parcels 24 hours per day (in contrary to the normal human delivery window hours from 9 till 22:00) and because drones are not

dependent on roads (McKinsey, 2018).

The last-mile delivery has been identified as a key differentiator for future deliveries. Last-mile delivery can be defined as the transportation of products from the last transportation hub to the customer. The current methods that are considered for last mile delivery are drones, autonomous ground vehicles with lockers, droids, bike couriers and the traditional delivery methods (Joeress, Neuhaus, & Schröder, 2016).

The development of light cargo drone delivery can potentially replace the traditional forms of last-mile delivery by eliminating the need for a delivery driver (McKinsey, 2018). Using drones for product deliveries, will make it easier to perform same day delivery, improve the reliability regarding delivery windows (plus making these windows smaller), will facilitate instant delivery, and will eventually be cheaper than traditional delivery, as no driver, car, or petrol is used (Tavares, 2019). Besides these specific benefits for the consumer, the use of drones will also be beneficial for the environment, as the current transportation methods are considered as one of the main contributors to CO2 emission (Koiwanit, 2018).

The disappearance of the delivery driver and the development of these new technologies with a high dependency on autonomous, independent technologies, can change the way consumers think about which characteristics are important for a delivery. This might lead to a more troublesome adaptation of new delivery methods by consumers. Consumers might become more cautious for ordering products online when they know that an autonomous vehicle will deliver their product, as the delivery is depending on the technology, that has not been widely accepted by society yet (McKinsey, 2018).

The fact that these new delivery technologies, and in particular drone delivery, have not been widely accepted/used has made us wonder in which case customers would choose for these new delivery methods (Rabeel Khan, 2019).

During the preliminary research, we noticed that no further research was conducted on the relationship between product options (e.g. price, type, etc.), delivery options (like delivery time, window, etc.), and the consumer's preferences regarding new delivery methods in rural areas in the Netherlands. The discovered research gap is acknowledged by researchers as well (A. Lawson, 2017).

Research showed that, due to the growth of e-commerce, the delivery characteristics, customer

preferences, delivery efficiency and environmentally friendly options are playing a bigger role for both the consumer as the companies (W. Yong, 2018). And that the variety of delivery options and the perceived quality of the delivery service are major decision criteria for online consumers and therefore can directly impact the choice for a certain delivery option, and directly affect e-commerce players' success in the marketplace (Joeress, Neuhaus, & Schröder, 2016).

In this paper we will examine the relationship as discussed in the previous section. Our research will be specified on drone delivery as it is a newly autonomous delivery method that has the potential to offer a reliable service for the delivery and collection of light cargo parcels in the future (Bor-Yaliniz, Salem, Senerath, & Yanikomeroglu, 2019), and because drone delivery is currently being tested in certain areas, we thought it would be the most relevant autonomous delivery method at this moment. (Amazon, 2017).

In this study, we develop a theoretical framework that will analyze the influence of the product and delivery characteristics on the customers' preference for new delivery methods. The results of this research can be generalized for other (future) autonomous delivery methods that can be used for light cargo delivery for consumers.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND & RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The research question diluted in this paper has been combined with several sub-questions with each sub-question generating knowledge to help fill (create) the knowledge gap as defined in the problem statement. The following research question has been created based on the problem statement:

“To what extent do product and delivery characteristics affect the likelihood of consumers using drone light cargo postal delivery in the near future?”

This research question is supported by the following practical & theoretical sub-questions:

R1: How do these new autonomous delivery methods differ from traditional delivery?

R2: Which variables can be distinguished in the product characteristics and delivery options category?

R3: What is the relationship between product characteristics and the likelihood of consumers

using drone delivery?

R4: What is the relationship between delivery options and the likelihood of consumers using drone delivery?

R5: To what extent do product characteristics influence the likelihood of consumers using drone delivery?

R6: To what extent do delivery options affect the likelihood of consumers using drone delivery?

Figure 1. conceptual model

CONCEPTUAL MODEL & THEORY

This research focuses on the effect that the delivery options and product options have on a consumer's decision to choose a certain form of autonomous vehicle delivery over traditional delivery methods. In this research a case study will be performed, using drone delivery as an example of autonomous vehicle delivery. The influence of the delivery and product options will measure to what extent consumers will use drone delivery and to what extent consumer characteristics influence this decision (figure 1).

These two categorized variables will be measured by conducting a survey among people living in rural areas and that order products online, with a weight limit of 5 kilograms. The 5-kilogram limitation is based on a '60 minutes' interview with Jeff Bezos, the CEO of Amazon, where Bezos claimed that roughly 86% of packages sold on Amazon weigh less than 5 pounds and that Amazon's commercial drones are capable of carrying packages up to 5 kilograms (CBS News, 2015). Our target group is aimed at Dutch habitants that currently live in a rural area, because rural areas are easier for drones to deliver packages to. This is due to the fact that in these areas relatively more residents live in detached houses (Park et al, 2018).

We included 'Consumer characteristics' within this model to measure its moderating effect on the consumer's intention to use light postal delivery. Consumer characteristics consist of one variable: age. A research from Valor & Sieber (2003) shows that age can be of influence on the consumer's acceptance of technology.

Delivery options

The conceptual model contains two categorized independent variables: 'Delivery options' and 'Product options'. The variable 'Delivery options' measures how the time until package gets delivered and the size of the delivery window can affect the intention of a consumer to make use of drone delivery. The characteristics are based on the results of Okholm et al (2013) where the effect of these characteristics showed a positive correlation with a consumer's E-commerce experience and therefore could be valuable for consumers when deciding for newly developed delivery methods.

The newly autonomous delivery methods differ from the traditional methods in multiple more efficient ways. Packages that are delivered through drone delivery can be delivered instantly or at most within the same day in normal situations (McKinsey, 2016). Possible high peak situations may be the exception but are less common (Christmas deals, Cyber Monday). Traditional delivery methods in the Netherlands take at least four hours (bol.com) and on average 24 hours or more. The hypothesis below is formulated based on this section.

H1: delivery time positively affects attitude toward package deliveries by drones

The time window in which a product gets delivered becomes smaller when using drones. Bamburly (2015) states that a delivery window of 30 minutes for deliveries by drones can be a realistic prediction, whereas the delivery window of traditional delivery methods can vary between several hours to a whole day. In this case, the broader delivery window may negatively affect the customer's satisfaction due to the uncertainty of the exact delivery time (Sharda & Voß, 2008).

H2: shorter delivery windows positively affect a consumer's attitude toward drone deliveries

Packages delivered by drones can lead to a decrease of the carbon footprint of the parcel delivery industry. The exact gained efficiency of drones compared to traditional delivery methods is hard to determine, as it depends on the number of miles to the service zone, and the power source of the delivery method.

In general, new delivery methods make us of less polluting power sources, compared to traditional delivery methods. The use of new delivery methods is expected to lower the total emission of the parcel delivery industry and have a significant impact on the carbon footprint (Stolaroff et al, 2018).

H3: a smaller carbon footprint positively affects a consumer's attitude toward drone deliveries

Product options

The product type also affects the customer's need for a certain product. Highly needed products are expected to be more likely to use instant delivery through drones. Whereas luxury items are less needed and consumers might not feel the urge to have it instantly delivered. The need for a product can influence the intention to use drone delivery, as people might not be aware of the benefits, performance and the potential of drone deliveries yet.

H4: A product category affects a consumer's attitude toward drone deliveries

Consumer characteristics

The moderating variable "Consumer characteristics" will measure to what extend the consumer characteristics affect the relationship between product- and delivery options and the consumers intention to make use of drone delivery. Research has shown that younger people are more likely to try out new technologies, compared to elderly people (Valor & Sieber, 2003).

H5: A younger age positively affects a consumer's attitude toward drone deliveries.

METHODS

The goal of the research is to identify the preferences of a large group of consumers living in rural areas. It is impossible to measure the preferences of the whole population, therefore a quantitative (survey) research will be conducted, using a non-probability sampling method. We have chosen for correlational research, as we want to identify the relationship between product characteristics and delivery options, with the intention of a consumer's choosing for drone delivery as output. To receive valid data regarding the consumer preferences, survey research is the most suitable and relevant option.

For deciding the survey mode, we have worked through multiple steps. At first, we decided that the survey should be self-administration, because a large group of people has to be addressed, in a short amount of time, and because only predefined structured information is demanded, there is no need for interaction, because the surveys consists of basic, easy-to-understand questions Self-administered surveys are electronic, which made it less time consuming for us. Within the self-administered, we chose for a location-based survey, as the research focuses on the preferences of people living in rural areas.

We have composed a survey, which we have conducted among 31 people who live in a rural area. The sample size of the population to conduct the survey on has been based on the non-probability method: convenience sampling. We chose for this sampling method, as the time for the research was limited, and this was the fastest and most inexpensive method for us to gather the data.

The sample size of our target group is calculated using the number of people living in rural areas in the Netherlands, a confidence interval of 5 and a confidence level of 95%. Data retrieved from the CBS is used to calculate the sample size via an online sample size calculator.

Population	Sample
7.975.000	384

Table 1. sample size

The survey data is anonymous and can only be assessed by the researcher, and the reviewers. If other researchers are interested in the data, they can contact the original researchers. The data is stored in a google drive and on the personal computers of the researchers. The storage should not lead to any privacy-related issues. The results of the data

analysis will be discussed in the paper.

Survey questions

The goal of the survey is to identify the preferences of consumers living in rural areas regarding same-day delivery of their online purchases by drones. The data retrieved through the survey will form the statistical basis for a framework to calculate the likelihood of a predefined target group using same-day delivery with a predefined newly introduced delivery method. The survey is composed as such, to use the results and provide statistics to this framework. The survey consists of 12 questions, and helped to retrieve consumer information, learn about their delivery preferences and which product characteristics are affecting their choices. The survey includes only closed-ended questions and both single- and multi-item measures. The survey questions can be found in the appendix. The product categories used in the research are based on statistics from the CBS including the five product categories that are most ordered in the NL (Centraal Bureau voor Statistiek, 2019).

These categories are:

- Cosmetics and cleaning products;
- Clothes and sport attributes;
- Books, magazines and newspapers;
- Hardware and electronic devices;
- Household goods and other devices.

The survey includes different rating scales in order to apply statistics on the survey data. The types of scales used in the survey are a dichotomous scale, forced choice scale, Likert scale, and category scale. The used scales are chosen based on the type of question.

Validity and reliability

Due to the limited time of the research, the survey is conducted among a sample that was sampled using the non-probability method, convenience sampling. This method has a low generalizability, and therefore a lower external validity.

The survey is constructed especially for this research, in order to guarantee the validity of the research. In order to ensure the reliability of the research, a retest can be performed by replicating the survey among people from the population. Due to the limited time for this research, we were not able to perform this replaceability test, or conduct the surveys among the whole sample. The

reliability of the consistency of the measure variables can be determined for this research by calculating the inter-item consistency reliability.

RESULTS

Our collected data were combined and analysed in order to draw conclusions about our hypotheses. This chapter will go in depth about our data analysis process and our conclusions.

Data analysis process

In order to stay compliant with the GDPR, we collected as little personal data as possible and only collected the data that was necessary for this research. All collected data has been depersonalized and cannot be used to trace back the interviewees. All gathered data have been safely stored on a laptop installed with Bitlocker and only the researchers have had access to the data.

After collecting the data, we used SPSS to analyze the data. Since the sample size contained more than 30 respondents, we assumed that the findings were normally distributed.

Findings

Based on the gathered data, we were able to draw conclusions about our hypotheses. Table 2 shows a short summary about the conclusions of these hypotheses. The survey data shows that only two variables are significant for determining a consumer's intention to use light cargo drone delivery.

We were able to conclude that delivery time positively affects a consumer's attitude toward drone deliveries with 99.7% confidence. The data showed that the respondents were more likely to pay more for faster deliveries when their packages get delivered via drones. The speed of the delivery can therefore play an important role for the adoption of drone delivery by consumers.

We were not able to conclude that a shorter delivery window has a significant effect on our dependent variable. The respondents were not more likely to choose for drone delivery, when a smaller delivery window is one of the benefits of drone deliveries compared to the traditional delivery methods.

Our data showed a significant correlation between a smaller carbon footprint and a consumer's intention to choose for drone delivery. The significance level of .052 shows the importance of a reduced carbon footprint for consumers.

The data did not support the hypothesis that a chosen product category affects the consumer's intention to choose for drone delivery. There seems to be no difference between the categories: cosmetics, clothes, books, hardware and household goods.

H	HYPOTHESIS STATEMENT	SUPPORTED BY THE DATA (YES/NO)	SIGNIFICANCE LEVEL
H1	Delivery time positively affects attitude toward package deliveries by drones	Yes	.003
H2	Shorter delivery windows positively affect a consumer's attitude toward drone deliveries	No	.477
H3	A smaller carbon footprint positively affects a consumer's attitude toward drone deliveries	Yes	.052
H4	A product category affects a consumer's attitude toward drone deliveries	No	Cosmetics: .933 Clothes: .153 Books: .303 Hardware: .191 Household goods: .276
H5	A younger age positively affects a consumer's attitude toward drone deliveries.	No	Under 18: .237 18-26: 0.476 27-34: 0.913 35-54: 0.641 55-64: no data 64+: no data

Table 2. Hypotheses results

DISCUSSION

This research is relevant for academics but also for managers. The academics can further investigate which characteristics determine the consumer's choice to choose a delivery method that is environmentally friendly and can deliver in a short period of time, on the same day. For managers it is relevant to note for which products, consumers would like to pay an x-amount more for a delivery method that delivers on the same day. Managers can therefore choose whether, for example, drone delivery is useful for their business.

As mentioned in the results, we used a sample of thirty people. This is the minimum number of participants to assume that the sample is normally distributed. Due to the relatively small sample, the results of this study cannot be generalized for the entire population. This is also because we only sampled people who lived in a rural area. We chose this sample because in a rural area it is more likely that they can deliver to the front door. But this threatens the external validity. Another threat to external validity is the choice to use a non-probability sampling technique called convenience. Family members who were

"convenient available" were chosen to perform the study. We had to make these choices because of the short time frame in which we had to write this research.

The chosen product categories all belong to the group of 'luxury' products. These results cannot be generalized to products within the 'necessity' categories. This is because people are more inclined to pay a little more for necessity products so that they have them immediately, because they may need that product for their own health, like medicine or food.

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that a new frontier for consumer product delivery is starting. Research states that many new innovative alternatives are being tested. Combined with the rise of 5G networking these technologies will make their way to consumers in the coming years.

However, with these new technologies, consumers will be exposed to multiple new delivery options in which the adoption can differ based on certain characteristics. Current literature states that there is a knowledge gap on the influence of product and delivery characteristics on consumers choosing a certain delivery option e.g. drones. In this paper we have aimed to define the different characteristics which are influencing consumer adoption of the delivery method. We have looked at current literature to determine characteristics of influence and with this information we set up several hypotheses.

To be able to test these hypotheses, we have opted to conduct a survey research. In this research we have taken a convenience sample with 31 respondents. With this survey we opted to test five different hypotheses that we have set up. The results of these surveys show that only 2 of the 5 variables are significant because of the lower sample size. With the first variable we were able to conclude that the delivery time positively affects consumers attitude toward drone deliveries. Respondents were more likely to pay more for faster deliveries when their packages get delivered via drones. The speed of the delivery can therefore play an important role for the adoption of drone delivery by consumers.

Although, we were not able to conclude that a shorter delivery window has a significant effect on consumer intention to use drone delivery. Our data also showed that consumers are willing to pay more to help reduce carbon footprint for consumers. On the basis of the different product categories, there seems to be no difference between the researched

categories.

These results show that there is an importance and correlation between the researched variables and that new knowledge can be created which can help users with determining the expected use of new delivery technologies in correlation with consumer and product characteristics.

However, there is one shortcoming in the research and that is the low number of respondents. Because the sample size is relatively low for the number of predictors, not all measured variables were tested enough. Further research should be conducted with a larger and more relevant sample size to better predict the significance of the chosen categories. This can help build framework in which delivery methods can be tested.

REFERENCES

- Bamburly, D. (2015). Drones : Designed for Product Delivery. DMI.
- Bor-Yaliniz, I., Salem, M., Senerath, G., & Yanikomeroğlu, H. (2019). Is 5G Ready for Drones: A Look into Contemporary and Prospective Wireless Networks from a Standardization Perspective. *Wireless Communications*, 26(1). doi: 10.1109/mwc.2018.1800229
- CBS News. (2015, 29 september). Amazon's Jeff Bezos looks to the future. Geraadpleegd op 5 november 2019, van <https://www.cbsnews.com/news/amazons-jeff-bezos-looks-to-the-future/>
- Centraal Bureau voor Statistiek. (2019, October 8). opendata.cbs.nl. Retrieved from Statline: Online winkelen; kenmerken aankoop, persoonskenmerken : <https://opendata.cbs.nl/statline/#/CBS/nl/dataset/83430NED/table?fromstatweb>
- Emerce Logistics. (2018). Bezorgchaos als gevolg van Black friday. Retrieved from Emerce: <https://www.emerce.nl/nieuws/bezorgchaos-gevolg-black-friday>
- Joerss, M., Neuhaus, F., & Schröder, J. (2016). How customer demands are reshaping last-mile delivery. McKinsey&Company.
- Joerss, M., Schröder, J., Neuhaus, F., Klink, C., & Mann, F. (2016). Parcel delivery, the future of last mile. McKinsey&Company.
- Jurgen Schroder, B. H. (2018). Fast forwarding last-mile delivery implications for the ecosysteem. McKinsey&Company.
- Koiwanit, J. (2018, September). Analysis of environmental impacts of drone delivery on an online shopping system. *Advances in Climate Change Research*, 9(3), 201-2017.
- Okholm, H.B., Thelle, M.H., Möller, A., Basalisco, B. and Rolmer, S. E-commerce and delivery. A study of the state of play of EU parcel markets with particular emphasis on e-commerce. Study for the European Commission, DG Internal Market and Services. 2013.
- Park, J., Kim, S., & Suh, K. (2018). A Comparative Analysis of the Environmental Benefits of Drone-Based Delivery Services in Urban and Rural Areas. *Sustainability*, 10(3), 888.
- PostNL. (2018). Annual report 2018.
- Sharda, R., & Voß, S. (2008). The Vehicle Routing Problem: Latest Advances and New Challenges. *Operations Research/Computer Science Interfaces*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-77778-8>
- Schröder, J., Heid, B., Neuhaus, F., Kässer, M., Klink, C., & Tatomir, S. (2018). Fast forwarding last-mile delivery – implications for the ecosystem. Retrieved from
- Stolaroff, J.K., Samaras, C., O'Neill, E.R. et al. Energy use and life cycle greenhouse gas emissions of drones for commercial package delivery. *Nat Commun* 9, 409 (2018) doi:10.1038/s41467-017-02411-5
- Weideli, D. Environmental Analysis of Us Online Shopping; Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne—EPFL: Lausanne, Switzerland, 2013.
- Yoo, W., Yu, E., & Jung, J. (2018). Drone delivery: Factors affecting the public's attitude and intention to adopt. *Telematics and Informatics*, 35(6), 1687–1700. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tele.2018.04.014>
- Valor, J., & Sieber, S. (2003). Uses and Attitudes of Young People Toward Technology and Mobile Telephony. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.459222>
- Tavares, Thiago. (2019). Comparing the cost-effectiveness of drones v ground vehicles for medical, food and parcel deliveries.

APPENDIX 1: SURVEY QUESTIONS

1. What is your gender? *

Male

Female

2. What is your age? *

Under 18

18-26

27-34

35-54

55-64

64+

3. What is your occupation? *

Employed

Unemployed

4. How often do you purchase products online? *

1-2 times a month

3-5 times a month

More than 5 times a month

5. What product category do you purchase most often online? (5 is most and 1 is least purchased online) *

	1	2	3	4	5
Cosmetics and cleaning products;	<input type="radio"/>				
Clothes and sport attributes;	<input type="radio"/>				
Books, magazines and newspapers;	<input type="radio"/>				
Hardware and electronic devices;	<input type="radio"/>				
Household goods and other devices;	<input type="radio"/>				

6. How important is fast delivery (for example next day delivery) to you? *

Extremely important

Very important

Somewhat important

Not so important

Not at all important

7. How much are you willing to pay to get your two most popular product categories delivered to your home on the same day? *

Your answer

8. How important is a small delivery window to you? (For example, a small delivery window like 14:00 - 14:30)

Extremely important

Very important

Somewhat important

Not so important

Not at all important

9. How much are you willing to pay to have your two most popular product categories delivered in a smaller delivery window? *

Your answer

10. Some delivery services are more environmentally friendly than others, how important is a less polluting delivery service for you? *

Extremely important

Very important

Somewhat important

Not so important

Not at all important

11. How much are you willing to pay for a less polluting delivery service? *

Your answer

12. With drones you can have your purchases delivered on the same day in a smaller delivery window. In addition, drones are electric, allowing them to deliver packages in a more environmentally friendly manner. Suppose you live in a house where drones are able to deliver packages, how much would you pay to have your two most popular product categories delivered by drones? *

Your answer